

Deliverable 7.2 Knowledge Transfer Plan

Knowledge Transfer Plan

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Abstract

The MSP4BIO's Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) ensures effective collaboration and communication with key stakeholders. It outlines the steps for disseminating the project's findings, identifies the target audience, details the knowledge outputs, and sets expectations for future engagements. Central to the KTP is the dissemination of the integrated ecological-socio-economic management framework, aimed at informing and enhancing MSP practices. By fostering a dialogue-rich environment through workshops, webinars, presentations, the community of practices, and other engagement activities, MSP4BIO aspires to have a broad and beneficial impact on marine conservation and MSP efforts.

Keywords

Knowledge Transfer Plan, Dissemination, Stakeholder engagement

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Acronyms

CoP: Community of practice

CSO: Civil society organisations

EEZ: Exclusive economic zone

EBSA: Ecologically or biologically significant marine area

ESE: Ecological-socio-economic

EU: European Union

IP: Intellectual property

KTP: Knowledge transfer plan

MPA: Marine protected area

MSP: Maritime spatial planning

OECM: Other effective area-based conservation measures

WP: Work package

Glossary

Audience: the broader group of individuals or entities that could benefit from or be interested in the project's findings, outputs, and activities. This includes direct and indirect beneficiaries who might not actively participate in the project but are impacted by its results.

Beneficiaries: individuals, groups, or organisations that stand to gain advantages, benefits, or positive outcomes from the project. Beneficiaries may include direct recipients of project outputs, such as end-users, as well as indirect beneficiaries who experience secondary or long-term benefits as a result of the project's success.

Civil society organisations: independent groups formed by individuals to advocate for social, environmental, and community interests. They encompass non-profits, charities, non-governmental organisations, advocacy groups, and more.

Community of Practice (in MSP4BIO): a collective of professionals established within each test site to facilitate knowledge sharing and contribute to the development of MSP4BIO tools. These communities ensure that the tools are coherent and effectively applicable within the test sites and beyond.

Dissemination plan: a strategic document outlining the methods, channels, and activities designed to spread knowledge and information generated by the project to a wide audience. The plan aims to ensure that the project's outputs reach the intended recipients and stakeholders effectively.

Knowledge transfer plan: a comprehensive framework that guides the systematic sharing of knowledge, skills, and outcomes generated from a project to specific target. The KTP aims to ensure that project outcomes will be utilised and applied in practice.

Recipients (target users): individuals, groups, or organisations that are identified by the project as primary beneficiaries and direct receivers of information, knowledge, and outcomes disseminated by the project. Recipients have a direct interest and are expected to use the project findings within their professional, academic, or community contexts or decision-making processes.

Stakeholders: parties with an interest or stake in the project and its outcomes, including partners, beneficiaries, community of practice members, policymakers, and practitioners. Stakeholders can influence or be influenced by the project's execution and results.

Executive summary

The MSP4BIO Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) report outlines the strategies and activities designed to facilitate the effective dissemination and application of the project's knowledge outputs to various stakeholders. The report identifies the main stakeholders, including maritime spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, researchers, maritime industry participants, related projects, environmental organisations, and the general public, based on their roles in MSP, biodiversity conservation, and policy formulation and implementation. The KTP provides a comprehensive approach to sharing knowledge, skills, and best practices through various channels, such as workshops, technical reports, conferences, policy briefs, academic publications, newsletters, webinars, and social media. The report also discusses the progress of submitted deliverables and planned activities.

The KTP aims to foster collaboration and engagement among stakeholders, ensuring that the project's findings have a broad and beneficial impact. Looking forward, MSP4BIO is set to deepen its dissemination activities, focusing on interactive materials, broadening stakeholder participation, and enhancing the practical applicability of its findings. The project's future direction aims to overcome current challenges through more structured communication plans, engaging a wider array of sectors, and simplifying complex concepts for broader understanding. By adapting its strategies and maintaining a focus on collaborative efforts, MSP4BIO strives to make significant advancements in marine biodiversity conservation within MSP.

I. Introduction

1) Objectives of the deliverable

The MSP4BIO project is dedicated to addressing a critical global challenge: **conserving marine biodiversity and ensuring sustainable maritime activities through ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning (MSP)**. With the expected growth in sectors like marine renewable energies and shipping (IEA, 2019; UNCTAD, 2020), it is crucial to balance economic development with environmental protection. The marine environment in Europe, as well as globally, is deteriorating (EEA, 2020; IPBES, 2019; Pereira et al., 2012); highlighting the urgent need for solutions that both protect and restore it while allowing for some sustainable economic expansion. This aligns with the European Union (EU)'s maritime and environmental policies (e.g., EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Directive 2008/56/EC, Directive 2014/89/EU, EU strategy on offshore renewable energy).

To help address these challenges, the MSP4BIO consortium is developing an integrated ecological-socio-economic (ESE) management framework for the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems through MSP in cooperation with its Communities of Practice (CoPs) established in each of the six test sites. Effective knowledge sharing through established CoPs and other means with key stakeholders—including policymakers, maritime spatial planners, marine protected area (MPA) managers, maritime industry participants, researchers, civil society organisations (CSO), related projects, and the general public—is crucial. **Our Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) is central to this effort, outlining steps for dissemination, identifying the target audience, detailing the knowledge output, and setting expectations for future engagements (see Figure 1)**. The KTP is designed to foster a collaborative and informed approach, ensuring that the project's findings have a broad and beneficial impact.

The KTP of the UNITED project defines knowledge transfer as a “variety of activities which aim to capture, pass on and generate knowledge, skills and competences between those who generate them and those who can use them” (UNITED, 2022). Inspired by this approach, the MSP4BIO KTP is a strategic framework used to share our knowledge, skills, and best practices. It is designed for both internal and external use. **This deliverable provides detailed information on MSP4BIO's dissemination activities, the applicability of findings from each test site, performance metrics related to our communication and dissemination goals, and insights into the profiles of our stakeholders.**

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Figure 1. Knowledge transfer framework of the MSP4BIO project.

2) Principles of this knowledge transfer plan

MSP4BIO is an EU-funded research project, meaning that it adheres strictly to the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#). Our research activities are guided by the core principles of this Code: reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability. These principles, along with good research practices, are integral to our processes of dissemination and knowledge sharing. **We are committed to ensuring that our communications are transparent, fair, comprehensive, and unbiased.**

In line with these principles, MSP4BIO has developed a strategy for addressing ethics and intellectual property (IP) rights in the project (Deliverable 1.1). The strategy ensures consistent application of legal and ethical frameworks and assists the full partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects, including the 'do no significant harm' principle and IP rights protection. We are committed to upholding these standards of integrity throughout the project.

The KTP for the MSP4BIO project is founded on several key principles (see Figure 2) to ensure that the transfer of knowledge is not only effective but also aligns with our commitment to ethical and responsible research practices:

- **Inclusivity and engagement:** We are strongly committed to an inclusive knowledge transfer approach. Our goal is to engage a broad spectrum of stakeholders, striving to make the knowledge we disseminate reachable and accessible by all of them. This approach is vital to foster a broad understanding and collaborative efforts in MSP.
- **Clarity and accessibility:** We intend to present information through the KTP in a way that is clear, concise, and easily accessible to both specialists and non-specialists. This involves using plain language and visual aids, aiming to make complex scientific findings comprehensible and relevant to diverse audiences.
- **Timeliness and relevance:** Our knowledge transfer is characterised by its timeliness, with findings and insights shared at strategic moments in the project's lifecycle. We are focused on providing information that is both current and pertinent to ongoing MSP and environmental protection discussions and decisions.
- **Feedback and adaptation:** One of the KTP's objective is also to incorporate mechanisms for feedback from stakeholders. Feedback is very useful to continually adapt and improve our knowledge transfer processes, so that they remain effective and responsive to the needs and expectations of different audiences.
- **Transparency and trust:** In line with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, we conduct all knowledge transfer activities with utmost transparency. This approach fosters trust and allows stakeholders to depend on the reliability and integrity of the information we share.
- **Sustainability and long-term impact:** We are committed to ensuring that the benefits of knowledge transfer extend beyond the life of the MSP4BIO project. This involves creating channels and resources for knowledge sharing that will continue to support marine biodiversity conservation and sustainable maritime activities into the future.

Figure 2. Summary of the key MSP4BIO principles.

II. MSP4BIO stakeholders

1) Profile of the stakeholders

MSP4BIO stakeholders were identified based on their roles in MSP, biodiversity conservation, and policy formulation and implementation. The diverse groups encompass maritime spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, researchers, maritime industry stakeholders, related projects, CSOs, and the general public (see Table 1). Each group was chosen for their direct influence, involvement, or stake in ecosystem-based management, their capacity to implement or be impacted by conservation strategies, and their potential to benefit from and contribute to the project's objectives (UNESCO-IOC, 2021). The selection aimed to ensure comprehensive engagement across all sectors related to MSP and marine biodiversity conservation, facilitating a collaborative approach towards the efficient implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and achievement of sustainable development goals.

Table 1. Stakeholders' engagement plan: identifying key interests, target goals, knowledge needs, dissemination channels, and expectations for each group.

Stakeholder groups	Key interests	Target goal	Knowledge needs	Dissemination channels	Expectations
<i>Parties with an interest or stake in the project and its outcomes, which can influence or be influenced by the project's execution and results.</i>	<i>Primary concerns, motivations, or areas of focus that drive the involvement or interest of each group in the MSP4BIO project.</i>	<i>Objectives that the project aims to achieve with or for a particular group (e.g., engaging with policymakers might influence environmental policy decisions).</i>	<i>Defining the specific types of information, data, insights, or expertise that each group requires or would benefit from MSP4BIO.</i>	<i>The most effective and appropriate methods or platforms for communicating and sharing information with each group.</i>	<i>Defining what MSP4BIO aims to achieve or gain through the engagement with each group.</i>
Maritime spatial planners	Ecosystem-based MSP, MPA-MSP integration, trade-offs, blue economy sectors, multi-use, co-location of activities	Improving maritime spatial planning practices	ESE management framework, marine biodiversity data and metadata, overview of area-based conservation and restoration measures	Workshops, technical reports, conferences	Improved planning practices, sustainable space usage
MPA managers	Biodiversity conservation, MPA-MSP integration	Enhancing marine biodiversity conservation	ESE management framework, marine biodiversity data and metadata, overview of area-based conservation and restoration measures	Workshops, technical reports, conferences	Enhanced conservation efforts, shared use of maritime space
Policymakers	Regulatory compliance	Guiding policy and regulatory frameworks	EU, regional, and national policy analysis and recommendations	Policy briefs, workshops, reports, science-policy dialogues/think tanks	Informed policy decisions, regulatory changes
Researchers and academics	Advancing scientific knowledge, ESE assessment	Contributing to research findings (e.g., climate change scenarios)	Data, methodologies, ecological findings	Academic publications, conferences, symposiums	Scientific contributions, methodological improvements
Maritime industry participants	Economic development, ecosystem-based MSP	Promoting sustainable maritime industry practices	Regulatory trajectories, sustainable practices, sustainable economic opportunities	Newsletters, webinars	Adoption of sustainable practices, industry compliance
Related projects	Synergies, shared learning	Fostering collaboration	Comparative data, shared experiences	Project reports, joint workshops	Cross-project learning, benchmarking best practices
CSOs	Environmental advocacy, community impact	Facilitating informed dialogue and community participation	Analysis of maritime spatial plans, ecosystem-based approach in MSP, overview of area-based conservation and restoration measures	Reports, conferences, academic publications, blog posts	Increased awareness
General public	General awareness	Raising public awareness	Project significance, maritime impacts	Social media, public forums, newsletters, blog posts	Public support, community engagement

2) Analysis of knowledge needs and expected impact of engagement

Aligning with the goals of the MSP4BIO project: *"Improved Science-Based Maritime Spatial Planning to Safeguard and Restore Biodiversity in a Coherent European MPA Network"*, as well as the expected outcomes delineated in the HORIZON-CL6-2021-

BIODIV-01-12 call, the principal stakeholders encompass maritime spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, and related projects. The knowledge needs and expected impact of engagement for each stakeholder group are defined below.

Maritime spatial planners will be equipped with resources and tools, particularly the ecological-socio-economic (ESE) management framework, to enhance ecosystem-based MSP practices. Through technical reports, targeted workshops, and training, the project disseminates knowledge on embedding biodiversity conservation within MSP. It provides frameworks to help balance ecological, social, economic, and policy aspects. This engagement fosters more informed MSP decisions, with a clear focus on biodiversity, and lays a foundation for future national and transnational MSP initiatives.

MPA managers will receive support through insights into MSP and MPA integration strategies, the ecological toolkit, the ESE management framework, and the overview of available relevant marine data. MSP4BIO offers training and access to decision-support tools. This effort is directed at contributing to additional MPA designation, mitigating human activity impacts, and exploring multi-use approaches, thereby enhancing the protection of marine ecosystems and their services.

Policymakers will be provided with in-depth analysis on the coherence, effectiveness, and gaps of marine biodiversity conservation in maritime and environmental policies, complemented by workshops and policy briefs. This strategic engagement seeks to weave biodiversity conservation into policymaking. By providing recommendations and solutions to enhance marine biodiversity conservation within EU, regional, and national policies, MSP4BIO aids in crafting more effective policy strategies and promoting an inclusive approach to maritime governance.

Related projects will stand to benefit from a collaborative framework that emphasises best practices in knowledge sharing and joint analytical efforts. MSP4BIO has organised workshops and its Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tank meetings aimed at facilitating dialogue and cooperation among projects with similar objectives, such as with the MSP4BIO's sister projects, MPA Europe and MarinePlan (see Annex 1) and other related ones, such as MSP Green, eMSP-NBSR, MSP-OR, BLUE4ALL, Protect Baltic and future Mission Ocean Blue Parks projects. Access to shared data and tools enables a collective move towards adaptable management strategies that consider ecological and socio-economic trade-offs, thereby enriching ecosystem-based MSP processes.

III. Knowledge transfer methods and strategies

1) Knowledge inputs

The MSP4BIO project's knowledge inputs are derived from extensive research, data compilation, and stakeholder engagement. Key knowledge inputs include reviews and analysis of relevant marine data, ecological criteria, area-based protection and restoration measures, climate change drivers, environmental and maritime policies (at the EU, regional and national level), test sites' needs, and feedback mechanisms. MSP4BIO has leveraged a wealth of data and insights to inform the integrated ESE management framework.

2) Knowledge outputs

Among the five most relevant MSP4BIO's work packages (WP) in terms of knowledge transfer and application in MSP, eleven deliverables have been submitted to date. The following is a non-exhaustive list summarising the knowledge outputs generated, with submitted deliverables highlighted in green, upcoming deliverables in yellow, and suggestions or planned activities in italic. The CoP interactions and exchanges as part of WP5 are discussed more specifically in the Test sites section.

- **WP2 – Scoping and gap analysis**

Deliverable 2.1. has compiled marine biodiversity metadata from over 300 datasets, data platforms, models, and tools into a living document. This table serves as a valuable tool for various stakeholders within the MSP4BIO project, including data analysts, data managers, scientists, and marine spatial planners. It allows them to easily locate relevant data for their specific tasks, with entries classified by data type and MSP Data Framework cluster (Abramic et al., 2023), and linked to relevant desiderata. To further enhance accessibility and usability, VLIZ – the partner leading this task – has developed a user-friendly [web application](#), which facilitates efficient data search and retrieval.

Deliverable 2.2. has led to the compilation of criteria (including ecological and socio-economic criteria), species, and habitat lists used in policy documents to support decision making concerning marine protection, monitoring and restoration. To analyse the contents of the compiled criteria, they were categorised into themes (ecological, abiotic, anthropogenic, climate and socio-economic criteria). This compilation of criteria, species and habitats provides an overview of areas and ecological features currently prioritised for designation and monitoring in the context of area-based management tools. This overview has informed MSP4BIO's WP3 and WP4 and can help stakeholders (e.g.,

marine spatial planners, MPA managers, conservation practitioners, environmental CSOs, scientists, environmental analysts) understand existing criteria, their applications, current gaps and limitations.

Deliverable 2.3. provides an overview of the marine area-based conservation (MPAs and OECMs) and restoration measures currently employed across European sea basins. The objective was also to identify synergies between MSP and conservation measures as well as challenges in the governance of area-based conservation measures. This deliverable could help MPA managers, marine spatial planners, environmental CSOs, local communities, and other stakeholders better understand the current landscape of area-based conservation and restoration measures, enabling them to make more informed decisions when planning and implementing conservation strategies and managing MPAs.

A proposition for a course in WP2 could be "Marine Biodiversity Data Management and Analysis". This course would provide participants with the knowledge and skills to search for, manage and analyse marine biodiversity data effectively. Through lectures, case studies, and practical exercises, learners would understand the types and sources of marine biodiversity data, use data management and visualisation tools, and develop data analysis and interpretation skills. The expected outcomes include understanding of marine biodiversity patterns and trends and capacity to use marine biodiversity data to inform conservation and management decisions, including for MSP applications.

- **WP3 – Systemic approach to biodiversity consideration**

Deliverable 3.1. presents a systematic review of the scientific literature which addresses and suggests the use of functional criteria in marine conservation and restoration. The primary objective of this study was to identify functional criteria which have not been extensively considered so far in systematic conservation planning, thereby informing the development of a portfolio of improved ecological criteria for the designation of MPAs and ecologically or biologically significant marine areas (EBSAs). This deliverable could help policymakers, conservation practitioners, local authorities, environmental analysts, and researchers involved in the planning and management of MPAs, EBSAs, and MPA networks, incorporate functional aspects into their conservation strategies.

Deliverable 3.2. has developed a portfolio of improved ecological criteria, focusing on functional aspects and attributes distilled from D3.1, across different levels of biological organisation, to enhance the effectiveness of marine conservation, with the scope to integrate those with conservation criteria already in use. This portfolio presents the use of functional criteria in a conservation continuum (progression of conservation actions from assessing risks, to designing and prioritising actions, to implementation and evaluation), metrics, indicators, and methods with the objective to effectively catalyse actions to safeguard the ecological status of marine ecosystems, particularly in MSP4BIO's test sites. The intended recipients of this deliverable are conservation

practitioners, local authorities, environmental analysts, and researchers involved in the planning and management of MPAs, EBSAs, and MPA networks.

Deliverable 3.3. provides a framework for MPA managers and modelers to assess the vulnerability of marine species and ecosystems to climate stressors. The guidance is intended to address a range of management questions, categorised into three types and three levels, which have been identified through discussions with test sites and CoP members. This deliverable aims to support MPA managers and modelers in making well-informed decisions when integrating MPAs into MSP by providing a clear and practical framework for assessing climate vulnerability and prioritising management actions.

Deliverable 3.4. will develop an ecological toolkit designed for prioritising and networking MPAs. It will comprise advanced approaches, prioritisation criteria and decision support tools, categorised by conservation purpose, type of protected area and location. The toolkit will include an inventory of tips for decision-makers, highlighting the key elements, level of maturity, operability, uncertainty, and suitability for use in MSP, as well as the resources required for application. This toolkit aims to facilitate evidence-based decision-making for MPA planning, management, and climate change adaptation in the marine environment, benefiting a range of stakeholders including policymakers, conservation practitioners and blue growth industries. The ecological toolkit serves as a basis for the development of the ESE frameworks developed by MSP4BIO.

- **WP4 – Socio-ecological management framework for MPAs and MSP integration**

Deliverable 4.1. has developed a methodology for defining socio-economic and governance criteria to prioritise proposals related to new areas, boundary adjustments, area relocations, and network corridors within marine management approaches. The study aims to identify ecosystem services that encompass the social dimensions of various spatial management approaches in the marine realm, bridging the gap between human activities and the services provided by ecosystems. The knowledge output generated would help policymakers as well as researchers and practitioners involved in MSP and MPA initiatives (Pegorelli et al., 2023).

Deliverable 4.2. sets out the impact flow on ecosystem services of sustainable sectoral development and presents a non-exhaustive list of effective management practices tailored to each of the sectors selected for MSP4BIO: aquaculture, fisheries, marine non-living resources, renewable energy, and tourism. These practices emphasise the need to mitigate negative impacts, minimise ecological damage, and foster synergies among different sectors, activities, and the environment. The guideline offers stakeholders (e.g., decision-makers, researchers, maritime industries, maritime spatial planners, MPA managers) a holistic view of the intricate interplay between activities, pressures, and their consequences on key ecosystem services (Pegorelli et al., 2024).

Deliverable 4.3. provides detailed guidelines for a participatory-based trade-off scenario. These scenarios aim to assess and negotiate the consequences of diverse actions and strategies regarding the spatial and strategic management of marine areas. The outcomes, especially the trade-off scenarios, will be incorporated into practical tools and frameworks to support decision-making processes related to marine resource management. The method was tested across all test sites within the MSP4BIO project and will be integrated into the ESE management framework. It will help stakeholders involved in decision-making processes concerning MSP, management of MPAs, and maritime economy (Gutierrez et al., 2024).

Deliverable 4.4. will provide the ESE management framework, aimed at integrating biodiversity and natural capital into decision-making and MSP. The knowledge output consists of a policy analysis and strategic integration framework that supports the overall MSP process, including plan preparation, implementation, monitoring, and revision. The ESE framework focuses on a spatial prioritisation approach to planning and restoration of marine ecosystems. It will support the establishment, enlargement, and improved management of protected areas, as well as sector-specific analysis for the identification of measures and assessment of their socio-economic impact. The recipients of this deliverable are all the stakeholders involved directly or indirectly in the MSP4BIO project.

In the WP4, a workshop named "ESE Management Framework for MSP" could be organised. Participants would engage in interactive exercises and case studies to learn how to apply and adapt the ESE management framework in different maritime areas. The workshop's primary objectives would be to enable stakeholders to effectively utilise the ESE management framework, enhance its replicability across various maritime contexts, and contribute to the achievement of MSP4BIO's goals through iterative improvement.

- **WP5 – Operationalisation and participation in test sites**

Deliverable 5.1. investigated current gaps and opportunities in the consideration of biodiversity within MSP4BIO's test sites. Recurring issues were identified, including the need for improved coherence between MSP and MPA planning, lack of consideration of climate change and ecological connectivity, and insufficient capacity for stakeholder engagement. MSP4BIO will help address these gaps by contributing to data availability, integrating climate change impacts in decision making, facilitating capacity building, and fostering collaborative approaches. In addition to generating essential information for the project, the outcomes would benefit maritime spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, local authorities, and environmental CSOs, maritime economic sectors (Withouck et al., 2023).

Deliverable 5.2. aims to adjust the ESE management framework to fit the specificities of each test site, leading to the development of site-specific ESE implementation methodologies. The objective is to provide guidance for biodiversity integration at different

levels and stages of the MSP process, from inception to monitoring and evaluation. CoPs are among the primary beneficiaries of this deliverable, which is also expected to benefit a range of stakeholders, including maritime spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, local authorities, environmental CSOs, and maritime economic sectors.

Deliverable 5.3. provides site-specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration in each of the test sites developed in Task 5.3. It will provide solutions suitable for each site such as proposals for new MPAs, enlargement of existing restoration measures, as well as measures to address specific sectors of interest. This deliverable is expected to benefit the CoP members, as well as other stakeholders including MPA managers and planners, and maritime spatial planners. **Deliverable 5.4.** provides final recommendations, transferability and scale-up of effective biodiversity mainstreaming in MSP. The recommendations will be presented for each of the European sea basins highlighting key challenges, opportunities, and enabling conditions necessary for success, to provide the basis for scaling up across Europe. The key elements of the report will include a) the ways biodiversity attributes and connectivity can be considered in MSP depending on the local conditions, b) key pitfalls and enablers for ecosystem-based management of key economic sectors depending on the sea basin relevance, and c) key policy coherence considerations feeding into regional strategies. The transferability assessment will rely on a final validation workshop and science-policy dialogues to ensure the scalability of the ESE framework. Beneficiaries include all MSP4BIO's stakeholders and beyond.

Deliverable 5.5. will take the form of a report capturing the main lessons learned from the stakeholder engagement undertaken in each test site. The objective is to showcase effective methods and tools that worked in various local contexts, considering local cultures, environments, and other specificities. The report will provide valuable insights for future stakeholder engagement activities in MSP and MPA designation/management. The primary recipients of this deliverable include marine spatial planners, MPA managers, policymakers, and other stakeholders involved in participatory processes for MSP.

- **WP6 – Policy coherence and co-production of solutions**

Deliverable 6.1. presents a comprehensive policy analysis, which aims to understand the status of biodiversity mainstreaming in maritime and environmental policies at the EU, regional, and national levels, and identify related barriers and levers to enhance policy coherence and biodiversity conservation in MSP and in policies. This knowledge output is intended for policymakers, policy analysts, marine spatial planners, environmental CSOs, with an interest in promoting biodiversity conservation. It allows them to gain insights into the barriers and levers and subsequently devise targeted strategies.

Deliverable 6.2. will identify future directions for the EU, regional seas, and national implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy in the coastal and marine regions, building

on the findings of Task 6.1. The objective of this study is to develop concrete solutions that resolve contradictions between policies, promote cohesion, and foster synergy. This deliverable will outline clear recommendations aimed at various actors, delineating explicit timelines, the urgency of actions required, and the anticipated challenges in implementation. The focus is to provide actionable guidance for stakeholders at different levels, ensuring that the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy are met effectively across coastal and marine regions. The deliverable's recipients include policymakers, policy analysts, environmental CSOs, and other stakeholders involved in MSP, sectoral policies, and biodiversity conservation at the EU, regional, and national level.

Deliverable 6.3. will focus on developing policy solutions for MSP that emerge from the science-policy dialogues organised in MSP4BIO think tanks including sister and related projects, outlined in Task 6.3. This deliverable is set to propose strategies aimed at enhancing both horizontal coherences, across sectors and countries, and vertical governance coherence. Think tanks involving policymakers and the scientific community, including key scientific projects and initiatives, were organised.

Deliverable 6.4. will be a compilation of recommendations formed through collaborative efforts with other projects and initiatives focused on MPA and MSP. This report aims to showcase the key recommendations in a format that is both concise and visually appealing, ensuring that the information is accessible and engaging for its intended audience.

As part of WP6, a workshop will be organised to discuss efforts to support and improve MSP implementation in Europe. The workshop will present the outcomes of Deliverable 6.3 and Deliverable 6.4, which aim to enhance the dialogue and collaboration in MSP across sectors, countries, and governance levels. Participants will gain insights into the strategies that emerged from science-policy dialogues and think tanks involving key stakeholders and scientific projects.

IV. Dissemination methods

1) Distinction with the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D7.2)

Effective dissemination of the MSP4BIO project's knowledge and outcomes is crucial for maximising its impact on MSP and biodiversity conservation. The knowledge and results produced within the project are aimed to be shared with MSP4BIO's relevant groups and individuals, both within and outside the project, to help improve integration of biodiversity into MSP through the development of an integrated and modular ESE management

framework. This section outlines a comprehensive strategy for sharing knowledge, engaging stakeholders, and fostering collaboration across various platforms and formats.

The Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D7.2), delivered in Month 6, introduces the resources that will be available and the activities to be set up as the project produces and gathers results. Key activities include the organisation of workshops, training sessions, webinars, think tank science-policy dialogues, and focus group meetings, aimed at disseminating knowledge and ensuring the integration of project solutions into the work of key actors. To complement the dissemination plan, the KTP proposes specific strategies that ensure knowledge not only reaches its intended audience but is also assimilated, applied, and generates impact.

2) Work package dissemination strategies

This section is about the different strategies used to share or disseminate the knowledge and findings from each WP to various stakeholder groups. Table 2 provides an overview of these strategies for different WPs.

Table 2 Overview of work package dissemination strategies.

WP	Main stakeholder groups	Knowledge needs	Most relevant dissemination methods	Past dissemination activities	Planned dissemination activities	Feedback mechanisms
2	MPA and MSP planners	Overview of existing data, criteria and measures	Web tool, blog post, academic paper	Web tool, blog post	Blog post, academic paper	Contact information on web tool
	Scientists / researchers	Overview of existing data	Web tool, workshops, webinar	Web tool (data compilation app), blog post	Webinar, course	Contact information on web tool
	Environmental authorities	Overview of existing data, criteria and measures	Web tool, workshops, webinar	Web tool (data compilation app), blog post	Blog post, academic paper	Contact information on web tool
	Environmental CSOs	Overview of existing data, criteria and measures	Web tool, workshops, webinar	Web tool (data compilation app), blog post	Blog post, academic paper	Contact information on web tool
3	Scientists / researchers	Research	Academic papers, conference presentations.	One paper published, submission of abstracts for one poster and four oral presentations (accepted) for the European Congress of Conservation Biology 2024; Biodiversity and the Symposium “Biodiversity Change in the Anthropocene”	Two papers in preparation (organizing a criteria framework from WP3 and WP2; guiding designing of climate smart MPAs) conference presentations.	Conference presentations
4	MPA and MSP planners	Scientific review, stakeholder's interaction (CoP), guidelines for the nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors	Workshops, website, webinar	SeaSketch training in the newspaper; CoP interactions; infographics	trade-off workshop; BlueAzores webinar	CoP feedback on interactive sessions

WP	Main stakeholder groups	Knowledge needs	Most relevant dissemination methods	Past dissemination activities	Planned dissemination activities	Feedback mechanisms
	Scientists / researchers	Research	Academic papers, conference presentations, etc.	Presentation at the CoP interactions, submission of two papers (data gathering in the 1st CoP interaction on stakeholder participation and 4.1.D), poster presentation in the Ocean Decade Conference	4.1 and 4.2 a total of 4 papers, and at least 3 conference presentations. 4.3 two papers and one workshop	Conference presentations
	Blue economy sector representatives - industries	guidelines for the nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors	Workshops, website, webinar	Presentation at the CoP interactions, presentation at the conferences	4.1 and 4.2 a total of 4 papers, and at least 3 conference presentations. CoP interaction	CoP feedback and conference discussions
5	Community of Practice members	Gaps and opportunities for better protection and integration of conservation in MSP (see Withouck et al., 2023)	Interviews, workshops, questionnaires, email exchange, exchange over the phone	See Table 3	See Table 3	Feedback survey launched in January 2024 (see Annex 3)
6	EU, regional (sea basin) and national policymakers and authorities	Policy barriers and levers to mainstream biodiversity	Workshops, think tank meetings, webinars	Hosted two think tank meetings with other project partners and policy makers to identify synergies and commonalities with other projects, and to discuss policy issues	Blog post (see Annex 2). Two more think tank meetings are planned. Further, policy outcomes will be presented in several workshops and meetings	Think tank meetings and online workshops are used to refine-revise policy barriers / levers and recommendation. Approximately 12 persons attend the think tanks

3) Dissemination activities

The dissemination activities in this KTP are designed to effectively share our findings and engage stakeholders across various platforms. Through CoP interactions and targeted strategies such as demonstration sessions, blog articles, collaborations with sister projects (Annex 1), press releases, webinars, newsletters, interviews (Annex 4), and participation at events, we aim to maximise the reach and impact of our project's outputs. Each activity is devised with clear objectives to ensure meaningful engagement, facilitate the application of our research, and promote sustainable MSP practices. This section outlines these diverse activities.

COP INTERACTIONS	
<p>The CoPs serve as a dynamic forum for socially innovative participatory development approaches in the test actively involving local/national maritime spatial planners and MPA managers, regulators, researchers, and stakeholders involved in maritime use management for the collection of local needs and challenges, validation of ESE framework and co-elaboration of site-level solutions. These interactions are also a good place to disseminate the project's findings and enrich it with local expertise and insights.</p>	
Objective	To engage with the established CoPs to share and co-develop insights, methodologies, and outcomes from MSP4BIO, but mainly to validate the ESE framework and co-elaborate site-level solutions.
Knowledge to transfer	The ESE framework, potential site-level solutions, and final recommendations for scalability of project results.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and interviews are being organised starting from the needs assessment to solutions co-development and ownership. • Interactive and participatory mapping tools will be used for the application of the components of the ESE framework implementation depending on the local needs, and engagement cultures.
Partners in charge	CEREMA, CCMS, UAC, UCA, CNR, HELCOM, GMU, NIMRD, VLIZ, PAP-RAC, UTARTU, WWF-MED.
Expected Impact	Co-development of tools, testing, local validation, acceptance, and uptake of MSP4BIO results and tools in the planning processes.
Metrics	Feedback loops from CoPs.

DEMONSTRATION SESSIONS	
<p>Demonstration sessions will be organised to showcase the solutions to the wider audience with a specific focus on wider user groups: public and private decision-makers and those who are planning to be in these positions in the future (students).</p>	
Objective	To showcase the solutions to the wider audience and validate the interactive platform that allows stakeholders to explore different trade-off scenarios and provide feedback.

Knowledge to transfer	The interactive platform.
Method	Demonstration sessions on each of the test sites.
Partners in charge	Lead by SPRO and UAC and implemented by test site leaders.
Expected Impact	The scenarios visualisation tool is understood by planners and ensure wider transfer and take-up.
Metrics	6 training demonstration sessions and a total of 100+ planners and scientists involved.

BLOG ARTICLES

Blog posts (see Annex 2) provide an approachable and captivating means of explaining to a large audience the intricacies and accomplishments of the MSP4BIO project. We hope that these publications will help to clarify the science underlying our research and demonstrate how applicable our findings are in real-world scenarios.

Objective	To publish informative and accessible content that highlights project milestones, explains complex concepts in simple terms, and shares the latest findings.
Knowledge to transfer	The GAP analysis, the context in each pilot, the ESE framework, the operationalisation of it in test sites, the results of the policy coherence work.
Method	Creating an internal calendar of topics to write about, and publishing blog articles on the website (https://msp4bio.eu/news/) and on partners' sites, and then further disseminating in the project and partners' social media channels.
Partners in charge	Led by SPRO and contributed by all partners.
Expected Impact	To reach our target audience and beyond and help them understand easily the value of MSP4BIO.
Metrics	Readability, distribution (shared across at least 3 partners' channels) and number of views (20 per blog at least).

SISTER PROJECTS' COLLABORATION

Collaborating with sister projects through think tanks and workshops promotes knowledge exchange and enhances the scope of MSP4BIO's impact (see Annex 1). These collaborative events facilitate discussions on shared challenges and opportunities such as writing up of scientific manuscripts and joint outreach.

Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To validate from the policy coherence perspective all the tools and approaches that the project comes up with. To collaborate with other projects and initiatives throughout the project to cross-fertilize and identify opportunities for co-creation.
Knowledge to transfer	Tools and approaches that the project comes up with

Method	5 exchanges with policymakers and scientists from other projects and initiatives
Partners in charge	Lead by WWF MED and HELCOM, PAP-RAC, SYKE, GMU, VLIZ, UTARTU, CCMS, CNR, UNANTES, WWF MED, WWF-EPO, CORPI, NIMDR, and SPRO as collaborators.
Expected Impact	Co-developed solutions are taken up by the policymakers at all relevant levels and recommendations are considered in the next planning and policy rounds.
Metrics	5 think tanks organised and at least 2 collaborations coming out of them.

PRESS RELEASES

These carefully crafted announcements will aim to capture the attention of media outlets and stakeholders, highlighting the project's contributions to sustainable MSP, safeguarding and restoring biodiversity.

Objective	To communicate significant project achievements, milestones, or findings to a broader audience, including the media, policymakers, and the public.
Knowledge to transfer	Project achievements and milestones.
Method	Prepare and distribute press releases to relevant media outlets and through project and partner organization websites.
Partners in charge	Lead by SPRO and with WWF MED, WWF-EPO, CCMS, UTARTU, HELCOM, VLIZ, UNANTES, CORPI, NIMRD, PAP/RAC, UAC, CNR, and SEASC contributing
Expected Impact	Press releases that result in media coverage, increased public awareness, and engagement with the project.
Metrics	At least 3 press releases published by the end of the project.

WEBINARS

The creation of a series of webinars (with no KPI set) was thought useful to provide a platform for deep dives into the MSP4BIO project's approach and outputs, allowing for direct engagement with a broader audience than that of the project. Through these online events, we aim to and share detailed insights into our methodologies and findings.

Objective	To disseminate project results as these become available, foster interactive discussions, and facilitate partnerships.
Knowledge to transfer	MSP4BIO's aim, pilots, approach and results (ESE framework).
Method	Organisation of webinars with detailed presentations and Q&A sessions and the recording of the sessions for publishing on the project's website for people unable to attend to view it.
Partners in charge	Lead by SPRO and with WWF MED, WWF-EPO, CCMS, UTARTU, HELCOM, VLIZ, UNANTES, CORPI, NIMRD, PAP/RAC, UAC, CNR, and SEASC contributing.

Expected Impact	Depending on the topic, a deeper understanding and greater take-up of MSP4BIO's results and outputs among the target audience.
Metrics	No KPI set at in the Grant Agreement. At least we should have one webinar published by the end of the project.

EXTERNAL NEWSLETTER

The external newsletter serves as a periodic touchpoint with the project's audience, keeping them informed and engaged with the ongoing progress and outcomes of the MSP4BIO project, and general relevant news in the topics of MPA, MSP and ocean conservation in general. It is a curated source of updates, insights, and opportunities for deeper involvement with our work and its relevance in a wider context.

Objective	To keep external stakeholders informed about the project's progress, upcoming events, and significant findings.
Knowledge to transfer	MSP4BIO news, upcoming events, external news relevant for the audience, announcements (such as Mission Ocean-related news or available opportunities), sister projects features, and publications.
Method	Distribution of newsletter issues every 4 months by email to our subscribers and by further dissemination on the project's website and social media channels.
Partners in charge	SPRO
Expected Impact	Stakeholders are up-to-date on the progress of the project and main results.
Metrics	At least 800 people reached.

PARTICIPATION AT EVENTS

All partners have assumed responsibility to maximise the visibility of MSP4BIO and convey its findings and outputs to the relevant stakeholders relying on their strong outreach capacity. They have been presenting the project (poster and presentation) at relevant national and European events and in meetings with the CoPs.

Objective	To increase the visibility of the project and disseminate outputs.
Knowledge to transfer	MSP4BIO's approach, learning ESE framework.
Method	Oral presentation, poster or intervention in relevant events to talk about the project.
Partners in charge	All partners
Expected Impact	To create interest of MSP4BIO's results for future use of the project's outputs.
Metrics	20+ conferences attended, 10 + presentations given, 500+ people attending the presentations.

V. Test sites

1) CoP interactions

Six specific test sites present in all European Sea Basins were chosen as platforms to co-develop the integrated ESE management framework: the North-Western Mediterranean (NW MED), the Gulf of Cadiz, the Azores (Graciosa Island), the Belgian part of the North Sea, the Baltic Sea, and the Western Black Sea. Serving as validation pilots, the test sites aim at demonstrating and operationalising the ESE framework. This involves engaging key national and local actors in a co-development process through the establishment of a CoP at each site to facilitate effective interaction between stakeholders involved in MSP and MPAs. A detailed participatory strategy at the test site level is being developed in the Deliverable 5.2 Test sites methodology including the participation strategy.

Interactions within these CoPs have occurred through workshops, interviews and focus group meetings and are designed to encourage exchange, build ownership, and ensure the uptake of developed tools both within the test areas and beyond (see Table 3). This validation process within the test sites shall elevate the technology readiness level, thereby enhancing the practical application of knowledge and solutions. The efforts include reinforcing scientific understanding, conducting surveys, mapping, modelling marine ecosystems, and assessing risks of human activities on these ecosystems, all tailored to the specific needs and context of each test site.

Table 3 Stakeholders involved in MSP4BIO test sites and dissemination activities.

Test site	Main stakeholder groups	Local knowledge needs	Past dissemination activities	Planned dissemination activities
NW-MED	Public administration, MPA managers, scientists, international agreements (Pelagos Agreement, ACCOBAMS), fisheries, tourism	Protection of marine mammals against marine traffic impacts (collisions and noise), knowledge and protection of deep habitat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 CoP interactions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1: online meetings with French CoP, Italian CoP and international CoP (January 2023); 5.2: online meeting with 6 CoP members for Ecosystems services evaluation; 5.3: online meeting with one marine mammal expert to analyse trade off regarding marine mammals' protection in the Pelagos sanctuary. • Various bilateral meeting with public administration, experts, or scientists on specific needs (marine mammals, deep habitats). 	Development of two StoryMaps on deep habitats and marine mammals' protection that synthesises the available data in France and Italy on those stakes, the existing protection measures, and the challenges to enhance this protection.
Gulf of Cadiz (Bay of Cadiz)	MPA managers, public administration, tourism, fisheries, NGO, Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local community: the role of an MPA, the mindset is restricted to conservationist idea; • Main stakeholders: mainstream of policy framework and operation related to coastal and marine areas for both conservation and sector operationalisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 CoP interactions: 5.1 (Dec 2022-Jan 2023); 4.1 (Jun 2023); 4.3 (Nov 2023); and CoP assessment (Jan 2024); • Feedback to CoP member of 1st interaction factsheet in Spanish was prepared; • Workshop for 4.3: presentation of the results of second interaction in Spanish. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference Ocean decade: oral and poster presentation, April 2024, Spain (4.2); • Poster presentation on International Symposium on Marine Science, July 2024, Spain (4.1 & 4.2); • Poster and oral presentation on the 20th Latin American Meeting of Marine Sciences, August 2024, Brazil (4.1 or 4.2).
Azores (Graciosa Island)	MPA and MSP managers, tourism, fisheries, NGOs, Scientists	Climate change data, black coral distribution	3 CoP interactions, newspaper (project kick-off, SeaSketch training), infographic, MSP forum	Next CoPs, one webinar and workshop, one paper on Scientific journal, one paper
Baltic Sea	MPA managers, marine authorities (e.g., ministries)	Regional MPA management and coherence	3 CoP interactions, HELCOM-VASAB MSP WG presentations, conference presentations	Next CoPs
Black Sea	MSP Competent Authority, MPA Competent Authority, Environmental NGOs, fishery	MPA management plans, socio-economic criteria, climate change, cross-border MPAs	3 CoP Interactions, project documents communicated, online meetings for participatory mapping survey (SeaSketch training) and trade-offs analysis	Next CoP, one webinar and workshop, one paper in a scientific journal

		coherence, alignment of MSP and MPAs		
North Sea	Researchers, MPA authority, MSP authority	Integration of restoration plans into MSP	November 2022 - January 2023: interviews with CoP members; June - July 2023: exchange in person, via the telephone or via email about socio-economic criteria; November 2023: in person & virtual workshop.	Interaction about ESE co-development in June

Within each test site, engagement strategies, key challenges, and approaches to improve knowledge transfer are tailored to suit local conditions and stakeholder dynamics (see Table 4). **The process has faced several challenges, including stakeholder fatigue and logistical issues, requiring innovative methods to boost engagement and facilitate effective knowledge exchange.** By employing strategies like face-to-face interactions, workshops, and digital platforms, the project wants to overcome these challenges, promoting a robust dialogue and collaborative learning within each CoP.

Table 4 *Strategies and challenges in knowledge transfer across MSP4BIO test site.*

Test site	Engagement strategies	Principal challenges for knowledge transfer	Ways to improve knowledge transfer
NW-MED	In person interactions, workshops	Stakeholder fatigue, difficulty to bring to the national debates the transnational issues.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing networks and communication channels among Italian and French authorities. • Strengthening the dissemination of scientific results to the decision process such as MSP.
Gulf of Cadiz (Bay of Cadiz)	In person interactions, phone calls, workshop, summary of the main findings translated to Spanish	Align time availability of stakeholders with the time demands of the project; translation of the material; demands from other projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using a unique channel where information about the marine realm is centralised and coordinated.
Azores (Graciosa Island)	in person interactions, phone calls, workshops, webinar, interviews	Stakeholder fatigue, difficulty to attend online, stakeholders located in different islands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translating MSP4BIO materials. • Developing more visual tools.
Baltic Sea	Online workshops by MIRO. Regional MSP working group meetings.	Time management with CoP members. Uniform knowledge transfer across the region. Coordinating and bringing together representatives from all Baltic countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More structured approach to communication and planning • Informing CoP members in advance about the schedule and number of interactions
Black Sea	Online meetings and in person validation workshop	Time management with CoP members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening the dissemination of scientific results to maritime spatial planners and MPA managers via more visual tools and practical meetings.

North Sea	Bilateral meetings, workshop settings, survey, email exchange	Stakeholder fatigue, mismatch of workshop content and participants, information about the workshop content was available too last minute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better planning, better alignment needs of the project from CoP members and expertise of CoP members
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2) Feedback mechanism

Surveys were conducted to gather feedback on the CoP members' experiences, identify valuable aspects of their interactions, and pinpoint areas for improvement. This feedback mechanism is essential for refining the project's approach, enhancing stakeholder engagement, and ensuring the effectiveness of the CoP interactions moving forward. **Feedback was collected in all test sites.** For example, in the Western Black Sea test site, participants reported valuable knowledge exchange and identified opportunities for improvement (see the Case example below).

Case example of feedback from the CoP in the Western Black Sea test site (Bulgaria)

This case example highlights the positive and negative feedback, as well as the suggestions from the CoP members of the Western Black Sea test site, in Bulgaria. A survey was conducted to assess their experiences, identify valuable aspects of their interactions, and pinpoint areas for improvement (see Annex 3). This survey aimed to evaluate overall satisfaction, the effectiveness of collaboration, the enhancement of knowledge and skills, and the alignment with local and national conservation efforts.

Positive feedback

Key points include the facilitation of comprehensive dialogues on crucial topics such as MPA Networks and the integration of MSP, serving as a platform for diverse opinions and expertise. **This approach not only enhanced collective understanding and fostered collaborative solutions but also bridged gaps between different stakeholders, demonstrating a strong commitment to inclusivity and collaboration.** Stakeholder involvement added credibility to the project, underlining the importance of creating a permanent collaborative culture. **The feedback also emphasised the usefulness of the methodology applied in identifying key issues and gaps, enhancing knowledge and skills in addressing marine conservation challenges, and valuing ecosystem services.** This methodology facilitated practical trade-offs with stakeholders and provided a better understanding of institutional actors' views on marine conservation. It highlighted the application of practical methodologies that integrate socio-economic with conservation criteria, contributing to a more integrated and realistic view of the impact of MSP and conservation policies. The feedback suggests that the real impact of these efforts, especially in connecting with the local context and providing tangible outputs to stakeholders, will become clearer as the project progresses.

Negative feedback

Key concerns include difficulties in uniformly applying all tasks under the MSP4BIO framework across the region, especially those requiring localised application. **There was a notable challenge in understanding and executing the exercise linking ecosystem services with socio-economic criteria.** Representation issues were highlighted, with low participation from certain administrative bodies and a lack of presence from companies engaged in strictly economic activities, excluding consultancy firms. The feedback pointed out that not all population segments were represented, and some CoP members lacked computer literacy, **contributing to participation fatigue and a decline in the credibility of participatory processes.** A sense of temporary commitment was noted among CoP members, aware of the project's finite lifespan, leading to reduced investment in efforts. Further, the feedback mentioned the inconvenience of signing consent forms multiple times and **suggested that the ESE concept should be articulated in simpler terms to improve understanding and translation for CoP members.** The absence of some key institutional actors from the CoP, whose involvement would significantly impact marine conservation, was also identified as a critical gap.

Suggestions

CoP members have offered constructive suggestions to enhance the effectiveness and engagement of the MSP4BIO project. These recommendations include adopting a more structured approach to communication and planning for CoP interactions, with advanced notifications of schedules and discussion topics to prepare members for more focused contributions. **Enhancing institutional dialogue and broadening economic and business world participation, especially from sectors like fishing, aquaculture, and tourism, are advised for wider stakeholder involvement.** Suggestions also emphasise the use of collaborative platforms for simultaneous responses in exercises, provision of comprehensive regional overviews, and independent resource gathering by task leaders to minimise disruptions at test sites. A reorganisation of internal SharePoint folders by test sites rather than work packages, along with clear case study demands, is suggested for better CoP interactions.

A dynamic CoP structure, with flexible consent processes and varying membership, is proposed to increase effectiveness. **There is a call for more communicative and visual materials, along with straightforward explanations of ESE concepts, to engage stakeholders more effectively.** Improving social and institutional dialogue levels, translating exercise results into practical recommendations, and ensuring continuity and coherence between meetings are also highlighted. Lastly, members suggest rethinking engagement models to be more open and less time-consuming, advocating for test site leaders to have the autonomy to select engagement forms that align with clear project objectives. These suggestions aim to streamline processes, enhance stakeholder engagement, and ensure the project's findings are both impactful and practically applicable.

As part of Task 1.4, regular internal meetings and workshops are planned to share concerns, best practices, and ideas, and to prepare as effectively as possible for the

testing and validation of the MSP4BIO ESE framework. This also ensures an efficient feedback loop. During the most recent meeting on 29 January 2024, MSP4BIO partners discussed feedback from CoP members and the organisation of the CoP III interaction.

The following summarises the feedback from each test site:

- Black Sea: CoP members expressed satisfaction with the interaction and demonstrated a good level of engagement.
- Baltic Sea: CoP members showed interest in tool testing and validation.
- Gulf of Cadiz: CoP members were engaged and eager to provide feedback, but moderating the discussion was difficult due to the large number of participants.
- Black Sea: not all sectors were covered, and there is a need to organise face-to-face meetings.
- North Sea: CoP members appreciated the SeaSketch tool, but some found the questions too scientific and technical.
- NW-MED: CoP members were not interested in testing approaches, but were willing to apply methods and criteria from WP3.
- Azores: CoP members were more engaged with the in-person format.

VI. Conclusion

1) Limits and opportunities

One of the main challenges faced by MSP4BIO is the diversity in regional and local contexts, which can hinder the uniform application of the project's frameworks and tools. Each test site presents unique ecological, socio-economic, and governance characteristics, necessitating tailored approaches to MSP and biodiversity conservation. Furthermore, effectively engaging stakeholders who have varying degrees of knowledge, interest, and influence in MSP presents another challenge. This is particularly evident in efforts to bridge the gap between scientific research and policymaking, where translating complex scientific findings into actionable policy recommendations requires continuous dialogue and mutual understanding.

These challenges highlight the importance of developing adaptable and flexible management frameworks that can be customised to fit specific local and regional needs. Using a variety of communication channels and methods is an opportunity to engage different stakeholder groups and to ensure that their needs and perspectives are taken into account. This includes leveraging visualisation tools, interactive platforms, and social

media to explain complex concepts and foster a sense of ownership and participation among stakeholders.

Furthermore, the feedback gathered from stakeholders across the project's test sites provides valuable insights into improving the MSP4BIO approach. By systematically addressing the identified gaps, such as the need for clearer communication of concepts and more inclusive stakeholder engagement strategies, MSP4BIO can enhance its effectiveness and relevance. Additionally, by highlighting synergies and collaboration with other projects working on MSP and biodiversity conservation, MSP4BIO can inspire and guide similar initiatives globally.

2) Future directions for knowledge transfer

Looking ahead, MSP4BIO plans to expand its dissemination activities by focusing on more interactive and visually engaging materials (e.g., StoryMaps and other visualisation tools developed by Task 7.4), broadening stakeholder participation, and enhancing the practical applicability of its findings. Future dissemination efforts will seek to address the identified gaps and challenges through tailored workshops, webinars, and policy briefs, aiming for a deeper integration of biodiversity conservation within MSP processes.

In parallel, under Task 1.4, test site leads are exchanging on the challenges, best practices, and doubts related to test sites and CoP interactions, and supporting WP5 for improved organisation of future CoP meetings. To exchange the knowledge obtained in each of the test sites, dissemination of Task 5.4's results, which will include the cross-test site analysis and assess the transferability of results and potentials and barriers for its upscaling, should be presented and disseminated to the CoPs. The task will develop recommendations for each of the European sea basins highlighting key challenges, opportunities, and enabling conditions necessary for success, to provide the basis for scaling up across Europe.

By continuing to leverage collaborative platforms and think tank meetings, along with exploring innovative engagement models, MSP4BIO will strive to maintain momentum in its stakeholder interactions, ensuring sustained impact beyond the project's lifespan.

VII. Annexes

Annex 1. Presentation of sister projects' goals and scope collected during the first MSP4BIO's science policy dialogue think tank.

	KEY WORDS	POLICY FOCUS	SCALE	CASE STUDIES/ PILOT SITES	IN HOUSE EVENTS
MSP4BIO	MSP MPAs Stakeholder Engagement	Achieving the Green Deal Integrating MPAs in MSP processes support implementation of EU Biodiversity Strategy and CBD post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Focus on biodiversity policy coherence	EU sea basins National, transboundary and regional level	One case study per sea basin	-Think tanks -Community of Practice Meetings -Project meetings -Trainings
MPA Europe	MPA Network Europe Blue carbon Biodiversity Smart (adaptive) MSP	MSPs to consider MPAs within a changing climate context European Green Deal Biodiversity Strategy and post 2020 Global Biodiversity Framework	EU Stakeholder engagement per sea basin (national and regional authorities - decision makers))	One case study per sea Basin <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 case studies to be agreed with stakeholders • no pilots 	In person workshop: policy brief on project outcomes and case study development. (Discussion with the stakeholders will lead to a policy brief + recommendations)
eMSP NBSR	MSP Sustainability Energy Biodiversity	Support coherence among MSP plans Cross Learning Green deal and impact of climate change	North Sea and Baltic Sea	Each learning strand has either 1 or 2 study cases. (Learning strands: Ocean Governance, MSP data, Monitoring & Evaluation, Ecosystem Approach, Sustainable Blue Economy)	-Community of Practice events per LS -Project meetings -Final conference -High level conference (TBD)
REGINA-MSP	Stakeholder engagement	innovations in the role of Regions in MSP contribution of MSP to the European Green Deal progress in MSP at regional and local levels positive interaction between MSP and the European Cohesion Policy	Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea Basins and EU Broadly	Murcia Galicia Sardinia Pays de la Loire Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur Crete North Aegean Sea County Mayo CPMR Members	-Training of MSP Authorities -Ocean Literacy Workshop -Communities of practice meetings -Case studies workshops with regional/local stakeholders

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	KEY WORDS	POLICY FOCUS	SCALE	CASE STUDIES/ PILOT SITES	IN HOUSE EVENTS
BLUE4ALL (www.blue4all.eu)	MPA networks Resilient and Efficient MPAs Blueprint platform	Restore EU oceans and waters	EU	25 sites across Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North-East Atlantic regions	-policy analysis -questionnaires -tests
REMAP	MSP Monitoring & Review Data Tools Models Data sharing	provide EU Member States with innovative technical framework for the support of the European MSP process Policy Briefs + co-development of tools with stakeholders	EU	Local - Galicia (Spain) Cross Border - Western Mediterranean Sea basin - Baltic	Beta-test of tools Galicia (Spain), Venice (Italy) and Helsinki Final Conference October 2025 Helsinki
PLASMAR+	Progress of MSP CIA development EIA Supporting methods Ecosystem Services	Macaronesia regional collaboration developing tools, products and methodologies for operative MSP	Sea-basin scale, the European Macaronesia	Azores Madeira Canary Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End of project Conference • Capacity Buildings • Stakeholder's engagement initiatives
Shetland marine plan	Marine Development Framework	sustainable development	Local scale - Shetland		Workshops
MSPGREEN	MSP EGD	Role of MSP plans as enablers of EGD Role of other policies (e.g. fisheries, nature conservation)	National level (analysis, actions) EU level (recommendations) EU sea basins (link with Sustainable Blue Economy)		Workshops
MarinePlan (marineplan.eu)	EB-MSP conservation EBSA Stakeholder engagement	integrate marine conservation into MSP processes in European Seas	EU	Azores Celtic Sea Western Baltic Sea Western Mediterranean Campania (Italy) Greek Aegean Bay of Biscay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high level stakeholder workshops (EU level) • planning site Stakeholder workshops • project meetings (Barcelona, Azores, etc.) • end of project conference

Annex 2. Example of a blog post published in the [MSP4BIO website](#)

Mainstreaming biodiversity into national sectoral policies – why is it difficult?

Biodiversity loss is a pressing global crisis. Unsustainable human activities have led to what many consider the sixth mass extinction, which includes the marine environment. To reverse this negative trend, it is essential to implement advanced biodiversity protection into environmental and maritime policies and practices at all governance levels: international, EU, regional, national, and local. This process of ‘biodiversity mainstreaming’ still faces certain gaps. In this blog, we explore potential reasons for these shortcomings.

Environmental policies addressing biodiversity loss

Institutions at the highest level, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Union are addressing biodiversity loss. The latest articulation of the EU ambitions in biodiversity conservation is the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Building on the Biodiversity Strategy for 2020, it was launched to step up the protection and restoration of nature and the implementation of existing EU strategies and legislation such as Birds and Habitats Directives. Among its ambitions, the new strategy aims to protect 30 % of the European seas and land, of which one third of the protected areas should be strictly protected.

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) are two complementary EU directives playing an essential role in the pursuit of the good environmental status of marine waters and in the sustainable planning of human activities at sea, respectively. The two directives should provide support to biodiversity conservation efforts. The EU has also updated other relevant marine policies, such as the Common Fisheries Policy and the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy to support the biodiversity strategy.

Therefore, this raises the following question: **are biodiversity considerations effectively integrated into the EU member states’ policies?**

Results from MSP4BIO analysis indicate that EU member states have effectively updated their national biodiversity strategies to align with the EU biodiversity strategy. **The national strategies, accompanied by operationalization plans, include long-term aims to improve the conservation of habitats and species.** They also acknowledge the need to integrate biodiversity objectives in all economic sector policies.

Integration of biodiversity objectives into economic policies presents challenges

However, biodiversity mainstreaming from national environmental policies to economic sector policies varies between countries and between policy domains. Even when biodiversity objectives are integrated in sectoral policies, significant gaps in their implementation remain.

The implementation of biodiversity objectives through sectoral policies is difficult due to four main types of barriers:

1. Institutional barriers

Conflicting objectives between policies is a common barrier to address biodiversity loss. For example, the current requirement to increase offshore wind energy production may overlap with marine conservation measures, especially in small sea areas hosting many activities.

The inflexibility of EU policies is sometimes seen as a barrier for realizing more ambitious biodiversity policies at the national level. For example, the Common Fisheries Policy still allows restricted fishing in marine protected areas, although at the national level there would be willingness to enact tighter restrictions on fishing gear impacting the seabed. Ambiguous policy formulations, such as missing quantitative threshold values, can complicate or poorly guide decision-making.

The incoherent division of mandates between organizations and levels of governance can hamper biodiversity integration in policymaking or implementation.

2. Organizational barriers

Coordination between governance levels, organizations, sectors, regions, and actor groups is often weak. **Policymaking frequently occurs in silos and stakeholder participation is poor.**

3. Technical barriers

A lack of knowledge can lead to poor adjustment of environmental policies to the specifics of economic sectors, resulting in a **deficiency of operational conservation measures.** Insufficient biodiversity monitoring leads to missing data and makes the evaluation and adjustments of policies difficult.

4. Resource barriers

Poor human and financial resources hinder the implementation of biodiversity objectives. Low environmental literacy may result in low prioritization of biodiversity in decision-making.

How can we leverage biodiversity mainstreaming?

MSP4BIO's analysis has identified the following levers to enhance biodiversity mainstreaming:

- High-level policies, especially those with a legally binding nature, support the integration and prioritization of biodiversity objectives in the policy- and decision-making of economic sectors.
- An appropriate division of responsibilities among ministries and authorities is important to avoid separation between biodiversity conservation and the management of economic sectors.
- Coordination, collaboration, and effective communication between organizations in policy formulation and implementation, involving stakeholders, is needed.
- Adding biodiversity monitoring requirements in policies would improve the data basis used in decision-making and facilitate policy adjustments.
- Clear policy formulations and adequate resource allocation are essential to overcome the identified obstacles.

Maritime spatial planning to enhance biodiversity mainstreaming?

MSP4BIO analyzed the role, potential, and limitations of the MSPD and its practical implementation in the EU member states for enhancing biodiversity mainstreaming and policy coherence. The analysis suggested that the link between the MSPD and the MSFD has suffered from lack of spatial clarity within the MSFD and a lack of coherence between the two directives. The EU has defined threshold values related to many of the descriptors of good environmental status such as recently for seabed integrity, which is helpful for MSP, but still, many other problems remain.

Keep an eye out for our upcoming blog post, which will delve further into this topic.

Annex 3. Survey to collect the CoP members feedback – Western Black Sea test site, Bulgaria.

1. On a scale from 1 to 5, how satisfied are you with your overall experience in the MSP4BIO Communities of Practice (CoP) interactions? 1: Not satisfied at all - 5: Extremely satisfied
2. What aspects of the CoP interactions did you find most valuable or beneficial?
3. Were there any challenges or difficulties you encountered during the CoP interactions? If yes, please specify.
4. How would you rate the level of collaboration and engagement among CoP members during the interactions?
5. Did the CoP interactions enhance your knowledge and skills in addressing marine conservation challenges? If yes, please provide examples.
6. Were there any particular learning moments during the meeting that you found especially valuable? If yes, please specify.
7. Do you have any suggestion on how to improve organization and exchanges during the CoP interactions, to make them more effective and less time-consuming for you?
8. Are there specific areas where you feel more guidance or clarification is needed?
9. How well did the CoP interactions foster a connection with the local context, including ongoing management processes, topics at stake, and the needs of the local/national actors?
10. How well did the CoP interactions stick to the context co-development and local/national validation objectives?
11. Are you satisfied with the work done in MSP4BIO in addressing the needs and priorities set for the test site in which you are working?
12. Are you satisfied with the overall progress in the project implementation?
13. Are there specific topics or areas you would like to see addressed in future CoP interactions to enhance their effectiveness?
14. Do you have any general feedback or comments regarding the CoP interaction in your site?
15. On a scale from 1 to 5, how likely are you to actively participate in future CoP interactions? 1: Very unlikely - 5: Very likely

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Annex 4. The MSP4BIO [YouTube page](#)

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